

Co-solvent controlled PVDF extraction from spent Li-ion batteries using supercritical CO₂

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ABSTRACT

The recycling of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) from spent lithium-ion battery black mass was investigated using supercritical carbon dioxide (SCCO₂) combined with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) as a co-solvent. Experiments were conducted at 70 °C and 80 bar for 15 min, varying the DMSO volume. Thermogravimetric analyses revealed that utilizing 4 mL of DMSO enabled the cumulative recovery of 55.6 wt% of PVDF. Thermogravimetric analysis confirmed a significant enhancement in PVDF extraction compared to atmospheric pressure (1 atm), where minimal PVDF was removed even after extended periods of solvent mixed black mass up to 18 days at room temperature and 24 h at 70 °C. Scanning electron microscopy revealed particle size reduction from approximately 93 μm to 43 μm and decreased agglomeration in treated samples, demonstrating improved particle homogeneity due to binder removal. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analyses confirmed that the chemical structure and crystalline phases of recovered PVDF remained intact. Despite its significance, PVDF recycling has not yet been established at an industrial scale. This study demonstrates the potential of the SCCO₂–DMSO system as a rapid, sustainable, and scalable approach for the efficient recovery of PVDF from industrial lithium-ion battery waste.

1. Introduction

A typical Li-ion battery (LIB) module has a plastic and/or steel casing that contains layers of cathode, anode, separator, and electrolyte [1]. A cathode contains cathode-active material, i.e., a lithium metal oxide, conductive agent (carbon black) and binder (polyvinyl pyrrolidone, PVDF) coated on an aluminum foil, namely cathode current collector. An anode contains graphite and binder (typically carboxyl methylcellulose CMC) coated on a copper foil which is the current anode. Those electrodes are separated by a polymer (polyethylene and/or polypropylene) separator immersed with an electrolyte containing a lithium salt (lithium hexafluorophosphate, LiPF₆) in an organic solvent mixture (ethyl/methyl carbonates). Once batteries complete their lifetime, they are collected for the recycling process [2]. The recycling process typically involves several pre-treatment stages, which may include module disassembly, discharging, thermal treatment, and mechanical processing, such as shredding. Depending on the specific recycling approach, these steps may be implemented individually or in combination to optimize material recovery. After the shredding process, a separation process takes place to eliminate large pieces such as the casing,

separator, and metallic current collectors (CC) from the processed pile, and the left is the black battery powder called black mass (BM) [3,4].

Recycling valuable metals from BM is quite important in terms of lowering the cost coming from raw materials and enhancing the material circularity [5]. There are several studies to recycle those valuable metals from LIB-BM, however, organic recycling remains behind due to their relatively low cost. BM contains organic binders polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), and Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), which lead to HF formation and/or carbon emission during high-temperature recycling processing [6]. Considering that a typical LIB cell contains 3 % PVDF binder [7], and with an estimated 5500 GWh (22 million tons of LIB cell, 250 Wh/kg [8]) of global demand for LIB cells by 2040 [9], approximately 660 thousand tons of PVDF from LIBs will be generated. It is known that PVDF recycling is not well established and ends up in the secondary by-products, increasing the costs for the disposal and risk of fluorine compound contamination [10–12]. To support a circular material value chain, this waste should be recycled rather than disposed of in landfills or incinerated [3].

One of the challenges of recycling valuable metals is separating the active materials (AM) from the current collectors (CC, often Al and Cu)

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because they decrease the leaching efficiency [13]. Even after their successful removal, residual PVDF adhering to particle surfaces continues to hinder subsequent metal recovery. CC and AM separation can be done mechanically [14–16], thermally [17–19] and chemically [13,20–22]. In the chemical approach, several types of solvents, such as ionic liquids [23], molten salt [24], deep eutectic [12,25] and organic solvents [13,20–22], were suggested for the delamination of the active material from CC via removal of the binder fully or partially. N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) is the common organic solvent for PVDF dissolution. Unfortunately, it has slow biodegradability and high risk to the ecological environments [22]. Overall, the scientific and technical challenges associated with PVDF recovery from spent lithium-ion batteries remain substantial due to several factors. First, conventional high-temperature treatments often lead to the generation of hydrogen fluoride (HF) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), both of which are hazardous to human health and the environment [26]. Second, PVDF recycling is not yet well-established at the industrial scale [12], with most of the binder ending up in secondary waste streams rather than being efficiently recovered, which in turn hinders the overall efficiency of valuable metal recovery [11]. This not only elevates the overall cost of battery waste management but also increases the risk of fluorinated compound contamination within recycling processes. These limitations underscore the urgent need for greener, scalable, and efficient PVDF recovery technologies to advance sustainable battery recycling. Numerous laboratory-scale investigations have explored organic solvent-based techniques for the recovery of PVDF from spent lithium-ion battery materials [13,20–22,27].

Organic solvents can be applied to electrodes for the delamination of active material layers from the CC or can be applied to BM to recycle PVDF. Both paths use the same mechanism that is based on the dissolution of PVDF in the desired solvent. However, the binding energy between active material particles and that between the active material and the current collector can vary [28]. Among different types of organic solvents, some solvents such as ethylene glycol (EG) [21], dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylacetamide (DMAc), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) [13] take quite attention as a green solvent candidate for delamination or PVDF removal process at atmospheric pressure. However, the conventional binder dissolution process typically requires elevated temperatures, exceeding 100 °C for EG, 150 °C for DMF, 160 °C for DMAc, and 180 °C for DMSO. Furthermore, when EG was used as the solvent, the complete delamination times at room temperature (RT), 100 °C, and 160 °C were reported as a few hours, under 2 min, and 6 sec, respectively. For other candidate solvents, PVDF removal yields from BM were around 33, 31, and 31 % meanwhile delamination efficiencies from cathode pieces were around 93, 85, and 93 % for DMF, DMAc, and DMSO, respectively. Sarkar et al. [27] investigated the delamination using THF:NMP 50:50 v/v at 90 °C and were able to separate the Al current collector and cathode layer completely in 50 min. Similarly, Bai et al. [20] studied the delamination of cathode active material from the CC using TEP solvent at 100 °C (60 min) and 150 °C (30 min) for cathode scraps and spent battery cathodes, respectively. Timewise, another study using 1,3-Dimethyl-2-imidazolidinone (DMI) solvent was spent 30 min and 5 h for homemade cathodes and commercial cathodes, respectively, at 150 °C [22]. The processing time varies depending on the starting material type, even when the same solvent is used. This is largely influenced by factors such as the thickness of the active material coating, particle size, and their distribution, as well as the presence of additives and impurities resulting from battery usage or pretreatment.

Alternatively, supercritical (SC) fluid technology is a promising method for PVDF removal from battery waste. Supercritical carbon dioxide (SCCO₂) is one of the common fluids in the industry due to its relatively low critical point compared to water. SCCO₂ itself acts as a solvent for polar molecules such as electrolyte solvents. The dissolving capability of CO₂ depends on its density which can be altered by changing the pressure and temperature [29,30]. However, Rindfleisch et al. [31] studied the solubility of low molecular weight PVDF with

hexafluoropropylene co-polymer in SCCO₂. According to the results, PVDF did not dissolve at all at 300 °C, 2750 bar because of the high cross-linking degree and molecular weight. On the other hand, CO₂ has very low polarizability and thus, it is a poor solvent for PVDF at high temperatures where non-polar dispersion interaction is predominant with respect to polar interactions [32]. Therefore, the dissolution of PVDF in SCCO₂ requires a co-solvent to enhance solubility.

Several solvents can be used as co-solvent in the SCCO₂ system. Yim et al. [33] investigated several co-solvents (DMF, NMP, DMSO, DMAc) for the SCCO₂ process to dissolve PVDF, and determined the optimal extraction conditions as 80 °C, 100 bar, and an extraction time of 20 min when DMF co-solvent is used. After 20 min, there were slight changes in the extraction yield when DMSO or DMF co-solvent was used. The use of the co-solvent DMF significantly enhanced extraction efficiency, resulting in a high removal yield of 98.8 % for the binder material. Moreover, using DMSO co-solvent for recycling showed a slightly lower recycling yield than using DMF solvent, however, new batteries made with the recycled PVDF using DMSO have better cycle life than using DMF co-solvent. Similarly, Fu et al. [34] investigated DMSO co-solvent for both PVDF powder and cathode pieces, identifying effective extraction parameters as 70 °C, 80 bar for 13 min due to reaching the highest solubility. Alternatively, Hayagan et al. [35] used 2x2 cm cathode (NMC622) pieces as the sample and used a co-solvent mixture of TEP and acetone (75:25 v/v) for enhancing the delamination of the cathode layer from the aluminum current collector. In this case, the optimal process parameters were 100 bar, 120 °C for 15 min for complete delamination.

Various co-solvents, including DMF, DMAc, TEP, and DMSO, have been explored in the literature for both the delamination of electrodes and PVDF solubility in the SCCO₂ system. In delamination studies, electrodes were cut from disassembled battery cells, while solubility studies focused on PVDF powder. Among the promising solvents, DMSO stands out as a suitable option, as it preserves the properties of recycled PVDF, making it comparable to pristine PVDF. Altering the SCCO₂ parameters (temperature, pressure, and CO₂ mole fraction) induces a volume change in DMSO, leading to the precipitation of dissolved particles because of its volume expansion (over 200 % volume expansion observed after 60 bar [36]). This feature can be used to recycle PVDF which was separated from the BM. Moreover, the miscibility of DMSO in SCCO₂ [37] and its classification as a polar aprotic solvent makes DMSO a strong candidate for PVDF removal in the SCCO₂ process. Polar aprotic solvents exhibit a significant permanent dipole moment but are not prone to proton donation, thus not breaking polymer chains through hydrogen bonding. However, their strong polarity facilitates the disruption of intermolecular forces within PVDF, thereby enhancing its solubility [38]. To the best of our knowledge, there is no study using industrial BM to recover PVDF with SCCO₂ processing.

This study aimed to investigate the separation of PVDF from industrial BM using SCCO₂ with a co-solvent, addressing a gap in previous research that primarily focused on PVDF powder or cathode pieces. The SCCO₂ with co-solvent is offering a rapid, relatively low temperature, and environmentally benign alternative to conventional high-temperature or solvent-based processes. By addressing both the technical barriers and ecological risks associated with current methods, this work contributes a novel process that advances circular economy goals in battery recycling. BM was chosen as a representative sample of industrial battery waste to enhance the practical relevance of the study. DMSO was selected as the co-solvent because of its advantageous characteristics. The goal was PVDF recycling by establishing a single-step process in which PVDF dissolves in DMSO under SCCO₂ conditions, followed by its separation through CO₂ flushing, contributing to more efficient and sustainable battery recycling methods. The research focused on optimizing the co-solvent/BM ratio to improve PVDF separation, contributing to more effective recycling strategies.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

In the experiments, BM was used, which was obtained through the mechanical processing of vehicle LIBs by TES SBS France (SK TES group). The received BM was sieved using a 500 μm sieve followed by washing with milli-Q (MQ) water (7 ppb, 18.2 M Ωcm at 25 °C). Sieving was made to eliminate larger particles such as long separators and plastic parts originated from the battery package. 100 g of BM was washed using 5 L DI water using a magnetic stirrer at 750 rpm at RT for 14 days. After washing, the mixture was filtered out using a paper filter (Whatman, 1001–125) and placed in a suction filtering funnel and Erlenmeyer flask. Finally, the washed BM dried out at 60 °C in an oven overnight. Four samples were taken from the dried BM with the quartering method and analyzed with thermogravimetry. The experimental process is explained as a flow chart and shown in Fig. 1.

2.2. PVDF removal at atmospheric and high pressure

PVDF removal from BM, at atmospheric conditions, was investigated at RT and 70 °C to compare the results with SCCO₂ treatment. The washed BM (1 g) was placed in a beaker and mixed with 4 ml of DMSO for 18 days at RT as triplicate. Then, samples were centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 20 min. With the help of centrifuging, most of the DMSO from BM was able to be separated. Further drying was done in an oven at 60 °C for overnight to remove residual DMSO. The same method was also applied at 70 °C for 24 h.

The SC fluid setup was built and contains a syringe pump (ISCO 260D, Teledyne ISCO) to provide pressurized CO₂ (Air Liquide, 99.9 %, ≤ 5 ppm w/w H₂O) and a thermostat (Model F10 & CM, Julabo), an 11.5 ml reactor (inlet has 2 μm filter), 2 and 0.5 μm Swagelok filters after the reactor and a sample collection vial at the gas outlet. Pressurized CO₂ was transferred to the reactor with a stainless steel 316 (SS-316) pipeline having valves. The reactor, made of SS-316, was heated to the desired temperatures by a thermostat (Model F12 & ED, Julabo). A thermocouple was attached to the reactor from the top side to monitor temperature which was connected to a data logger (TC-08, Pico Technology). The pressure was also measured by having a monometer assembled after two filters (Swagelok 2 and 0.5 μm). To prevent freezing

at the outlet, the temperature of the exhaust metering valve was maintained at 45 \pm 5 °C using a thermostat. The washed BM (1 g) was placed in the reactor with the desired amount of DMSO (≥ 99.9 % pure, Sigma-Aldrich) co-solvent which was 3–7 ml. After assembling the reactor to the system, the reactor was heated to 70 °C, and pressurized CO₂ was pumped into the set-up until achieving the desired temperature and pressure. After 15 min processing, the exhaust valve was opened and 115 ml (± 3 ml, given in Table S1) of CO₂ at 70 °C and 80 bar supplied from the pump to flush through the pipeline to transfer DMSO with dissolved PVDF to the collector (a glass vial). Finally, samples are collected from the reactor, filter (2 μm) and collector. Acetone (EMSURE®, Merck) was implemented as a washing solvent to collect samples from the reactor. Each experiment was performed in triplicates. The sample collected from reactor was having the processed BM, DMSO residual and acetone due to collection method. Afterwards, DMSO and acetone were evaporated in an oven at 60 °C for couple days, depending on the presence of the volume of the solvent. Dried BMs were analyzed with TG to calculate PVDF removal.

2.3. Measurements and characterization

Pristine BM, washed BM, BM from filter-2, and dried BM from reactors were analyzed with Thermogravimetric (TG) to calculate PVDF removal. TG analyses were performed by TA Instrument Q500 with 100 ml/min nitrogen (N₂) flow. Samples were heated up to 700 °C with 5 °C /min using high-resolution mode with a resolution of 4 and sensitivity of 4 which reduces the heating rate depending on the weight loss rate to collect accurate weight loss and temperature relation data. Once the system reached the set temperature, 30 min isothermal stage was applied. Then, the sample was cooled down to RT.

The removal efficiency was calculated according to Eq. (1), where R is the recovery efficiency (%) of PVDF extracted from the BM, and m₀ and m₁ are the PVDF quantities in BM before and after the process, respectively. The error bars of the averages were plotted using the standard deviation of the individual results.

$$R = \frac{m_1}{m_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Mass balance was also measured to see the distribution of DMSO and BM

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the experimental procedure.

in different parts of the experimental setup. For this reason, the reactor, filters, and collector were weighed before and after each experiment by a VWR analytical balance (SM2285Di, $d = 0.01$ mg). In addition to this, BM collected at the filter-1 was measured with TG analysis to determine the DMSO amount in the sample. The amount of DMSO was determined based on the total weight change of the filter, which enabled the calculation of the amount of black mass (BM) retained by the filter. Since only a negligible amount of BM passed through the $0.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ filter, it was assumed to be effectively zero, implying that the remaining BM stayed in the reactor. Consequently, the residual weight within the reactor was attributed entirely to the DMSO.

The presence of PVDF in collected DMSO from the SCCO₂ process was measured by ¹⁹F NMR 600 MHz Oxford magnet equipped with Bruker NEO console 5 mm QCIP. ¹⁹F NMR measurements were made with a transmitter frequency offset of -100 and the number of scans was 128.

Infrared measurements were performed to check phase differences by Perkin Elmer spectrum two Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectrometer with attenuated total reflection (ATR) attachment. PVDF (Arkema HSV1810) was used as a reference sample. FTIR samples were prepared from collected DMSO. 50 μL of collected DMSO was dropped on an Al foil, and DMSO was evaporated at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an oven overnight. PVDF films were formed on Al foil and were measured with ATR FTIR.

The density of BM was measured to calculate the mole fraction of CO₂ in the SCCO₂ process. For this purpose, the density of BM was measured by Micrometrics AccuPyc II 1340 gas pycnometer. Triplicate measurements were performed on both BM and washed BM. Each measurement has 10 sub-measurements, and the average values were used in the report. The standard deviation of the measurements was less than 0.011 g/cm^3 .

Bruker D8 Discover x-ray diffractometer (XRD) with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406\text{ \AA}$) was used to determine the crystal structure of the samples. The source was operated at 40 mA and 40 kV and the scanning angle was between 10° and $80^\circ 2\theta$ with a scanning speed of $2^\circ/\text{min}$ and step size of 0.02° .

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Quanta 200 ESEM FEG) coupled with energy dispersive X-ray (EDS, Oxford Instruments X-max 80) was used for morphological and structural analysis of the pristine and recycled BM under high vacuum. A secondary electron detector was used for imaging with 15 kV acceleration. Where necessary, elemental mapping analysis data were collected to determine the fluorine (F) amount change.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Investigation of black mass

Sample preparation was made via sieving the industrial BM to eliminate larger particles which are mainly plastic casing and separator pieces and then continued via washing process to eliminate electrolytes and anode binder. This was an important step in investigating PVDF binder recycling, otherwise, the nature of industrial waste makes it difficult to observe PVDF removal yield. The density of the BM was also measured to determine the mol fraction of CO₂ in the SCCO₂, DMSO and BM ternary system. The density of the BM after sieving was 3.12 g/cm^3 (dried at $130\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h), however, it increased to 3.32 g/cm^3 after the washing process.

TG analyses were performed in triplicate for both pristine BM and washed BM to analyze their content based on mass change as a function of temperature. In Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b, TG measurements in N₂ for pristine BM and washed BM were plotted, respectively. TG plot has three characteristic thermal regions that represent electrolytes at around $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [39], ethylene carbonate/electrolyte residuals at around $228\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [40], CMC around $285\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [41–43], and PVDF at around $460\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [44]. Therefore, regions were defined as RT to $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (region-1), 200 to $375\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (region-2) and 375 to $510\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (region-3), and plotted as dotted lines in Fig. 2a and b. According to the regions of 1, 2 and 3, the weight losses are $6.24 (\pm 0.53)$, $2.67 (\pm 0.13)$ and $2.36 (\pm 0.11)$, respectively. Under N₂ environment, the reference PVDF decomposes and loses 70 % of its weight until $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Arkema HSV1810 PVDF) [45]. Therefore, the total PVDF amount in BM was recalculated, and it was found that 3.37 % of BM was PVDF (33.71 mg in 1 g of BM). Similarly, washed BM was measured as triplicate via TG analysis and plotted in Fig. 2b. Weight loss in the regions 1, 2, and 3 was found as $1.06 (\pm 0.12)$, $2.35 (\pm 0.05)$ and $2.16 (\pm 0.15)$, respectively. The derivative weight change (DTG) peaks around $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $285\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were eliminated as can be seen in Fig. 2b. It shows that the washing process was useful to remove electrolyte and anode binder CMC, which is soluble in water. After the washing process, PVDF comprised 2.16 % of the BM, corresponding to a normalized amount of 30.8 mg per 1 g of washed BM. It should be noted that an additional peak was observed at around $585\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ after washing. It probably belongs to carbon black (CB) [46] and appeared clearly at a lower temperature because of the increasing surface area of CB due to CMC removal.

3.2. PVDF removal at atmospheric and high pressure

A set of control experiments for the removal of PVDF from BM were

Fig. 2. TG analysis of BM (in N₂ atmosphere) a) before and b) after washing with DI water.

performed at atmospheric pressure at RT and 70 °C. The washed BM was mixed with DMSO for 18 days at RT, in triplicate. The mixture was then centrifuged and dried to separate most of the DMSO from the BM. A similar procedure was also applied at 70 °C (24 h mixing). Treated BMs were investigated via TGA to find remaining PVDF in the BM and plotted in Fig. S1. Results showed that 29.99 mg (± 1.04) and 29.58 mg PVDF remained in BM after the process at RT and 70 °C, respectively. These results show that almost no PVDF removal was achieved at RT or 70 °C for a given time interval.

The washed BM was subjected to the SCCO₂ process as described in the experimental section. Mass distributions were made through the reactor, filter-1, filter-2, and collector for BM, co-solvent, and PVDF. DMSO quantities were calculated using both TGA data and balance. Few BM particles in the DMSO (collector) were ignored in the calculations. The mass distribution of DMSO and BM were plotted in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b, respectively. When the volume of the co-solvent increased from 4 to 7 ml, the collection efficiency of DMSO increased from 50.6 % to 76.4 %. The remaining co-solvents in reactors were 1.00, 1.63, 1.75, 1.87, and 1.10 g when 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 ml of co-solvent were used.

On the other hand, over 80 % of the washed BM stayed in the reactor meanwhile the rest were collected at filter-1. Only DMSO residue was present in Filter-2, between 0.1 and 0.17 g. TGA was made for BM in filter-1 and 37.51 % (± 0.68) and 1.05 % (± 0.12) of the samples were found as DMSO and PVDF, respectively. However, due to the resolution limits of TGA, it can be concluded that PVDF amounts from collected DMSO and Filter-1 are prone to errors. Therefore, only the BM remaining in the reactor was used to calculate the PVDF recovery yield.

Recovered PVDF amounts were calculated by finding the remaining amount of PVDF from the BM in the reactor. Experiments were conducted as triplicate and each sample measured with TGA and plotted in Fig. 4a. In Fig. 4b, derivative weight change (%/°C) were plotted for the samples processed with different volumes of co-solvent. The region-3 was used to compare samples since the decomposition temperature of PVDF falls there. It is clearly seen that when 4 ml of co-solvent is used, less PVDF (21.79 mg, ± 0.38) remains in the reactor which indicates more PVDF (9.01 mg, 29.3 %) were able to be removed and transferred to the collector via dissolving in the co-solvent under the SCCO₂ conditions. The removal yield values of PVDF from BM for all experimental parameters are given in Table S2.

One possible reason for the improved recovery of PVDF with 4 ml of DMSO could be the mole fraction of CO₂ ($n_{\text{CO}_2}/(n_{\text{DMSO}} + n_{\text{CO}_2})$) in the system, which were 0.43, 0.34, 0.26, 0.20 and 0.14 for 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 ml of used DMSO, respectively. Depending on the CO₂ fraction, it is possible to manipulate the DMSO-CO₂ phases within the binary system, and the

DMSO-CO₂ binary phase diagram can be seen from the reference paper [47]. According to the binary phase diagram of DMSO-CO₂, an increase in co-solvent volume leads to a decrease in the CO₂ mole fraction within the liquid region (except when 3 ml DMSO was used). In the liquid region, less co-solvent usage yielded higher PVDF dissolution per unit co-solvent volume, as plotted in Fig. 5. The liquid phase consists of liquid DMSO having SCCO₂ up to 40 mol% at 70 °C and 80 bar [47,48]. Ardestani et al. [37] showed, CO₂ acts as an anti-solvent when CO₂ mole fraction is saturated (52 mol% at 328 K) within DMSO/CO₂ binary system and precipitates what was dissolved in DMSO. Since decreasing the co-solvent volume increases the CO₂ mole fraction, more PVDF were able to dissolve without precipitation until it reaches to the saturation. Maybe this phenomena was another reason for the lower extraction yield when the co-solvent volume was increased. There was a sudden decrease in the increasing trend when 3 ml were used as plotted in Fig. 5. When 3 ml of DMSO is used, the system passes the equilibrium line and falls to 0.43 CO₂ mole fraction at 80 bar, 70 °C which consists of the liquid (94 %, having 40 mol% CO₂) and SCCO₂ (6 %, having 99 mol% CO₂) phases together. One reason might be the change of the existing phase in the system, from liquid phase to liquid-SCCO₂ phase. Another reason might be due to the lack of co-solvent volume per BM surface area therefore, DMSO traps between BM particles and not able to separate dissolved PVDF.

It should also be considered, with increasing temperatures, the Hildebrand solubility parameter of CO₂ decreases [32], which makes less interaction between SCCO₂ and DMSO (60.7 MPa^{1/2}, [49]). Meanwhile, increasing temperature yields better solubility of PVDF in DMSO. For instance, Yim et al [33] and Fu et al [34] achieved over 95 % extraction yield when they used PVDF powder and DMSO co-solvent (sample/co-solvent wt. ratio was 0.125 and 0.114, respectively) with SCCO₂ at 70 °C and 80 bar. Our results also endorse similar parameters for the solubility of PVDF from BM. However, BM comes with its complexity having various particle sizes/distribution, and other remaining organics might dissolve in the co-solvent. Such as, Fu et al [50] studied the liberation of the cathode from the current collector using 0.3 g of cathode piece (1x1 cm) with 4.4 g DMSO (sample/co-solvent wt. ratio 0.068) rather than using PVDF powder as the sample. When the sample was cathode piece, the liberation efficiency of cathodes due to PVDF removal was 96.7 %, however, only 60 % of the PVDF were able to separate from the cathode. In comparison, our work showed that 29.3 % of the initial PVDF were able to separate with the help of SCCO₂ (sample/co-solvent wt. ratio 0.227). Further analysis showed that 26.3 % of PVDF stays in the reactor as dissolved in DMSO. This part can also be separated using a post-separation of DMSO from the reactor.

Fig. 3. Mass distribution of a) DMSO and b) BM after the process.

Fig. 4. a) Average PVDF (mg) remained in the BM b) DTG (%/°C) of BM remained in the reactor. The dotted line separates region-2 and region-3, and the weight losses of the regions were written as percentages.

Fig. 5. Recovered PVDF per unit volume of co-solvent used (mg/ml) versus mole fraction of CO₂ at 70 °C, 80 bar.

Post-separation was made with a simple method. The remaining materials in the reactor were collected with acetone washing. Then let the BM settle down for 24 h to take the top liquid (DMSO and acetone) by pouring it down. This procedure was done twice. Then BM was measured with TG analysis and plotted in Fig. S2. The result showed that 55.6 % of the initial PVDF was able to separate from the washed BM. The collected top liquid was evaporated and a PVDF film formed at the bottom of the glass vial. The formed PVDF film was also characterized by TG and XRD. It should be noted that PVDF film from with the post-separation process, shown in Fig. S3, had a few BM powders residual that appeared as the dominant phase in the XRD pattern, plotted in Fig. S4. However, there is also a small hump around $2\theta = 20^\circ$ which shows the presence of the semi-crystalline PVDF. TG analysis, plotted in Fig. S5, also showed that the dominant fraction was PVDF for the formed

film. Thus, further purification such as filtering is needed to obtain pure PVDF.

3.3. Characterization

The pristine BM, washed BM, and SCCO₂-treated BM were investigated for structural and compositional changes with SEM. EDS was applied to three different areas within a sample and averages were calculated with standard deviations. The atomic percentages listed in Table 1, and weight percentages listed in Table S3. Results clearly demonstrated the F removal for SCCO₂-treated BM. There was also F removal with the washing process with decreasing P and S showing decomposed LiPF₆ were also removed. On the other hand, SEM images showed that the particle size was drastically decreased from 93 μm to 43 μm (the largest particle was picked, and their lengths were measured using ImageJ software), can be seen in Fig. 6a, b, c, and d. Fluorine map is also shown in Fig. 6e and f. Full spectrum of elemental analysis can be seen in Fig. 6g and h.

Collected DMSO in the glass vial was characterized via FT-IR to confirm PVDF presence and their molecular structure. Samples of 50 μL were taken from collected DMSO and put on Al foil in the shape of a drop. Then, those drops were dried overnight in an oven at 60 °C. A coating of PVDF formed on the face of Al foil. Those films were scanned using FT-IR and plotted in Fig. 7. Characteristic bands for α , β , and γ phases were reported [44,51–53]. Vibrational bands as highlighted by the vertical dashed lines at 883 (out-of-plane bending vibration of CH₂), 1075, 1175 (symmetrical stretching of CF₂), and 1408 (bending vibration of CH₂) cm^{-1} are the common bands for all three phases [21]. The vibrational bands at 483, 531 (CF₂ bending), 614 (CF₂ bending and

Table 1
EDS results in atomic percentages of BM.

Sample	F	P	S	Mn	Co	Ni
Pristine BM	50.88 (± 2.12)	3.77 (± 0.53)	2.80 (± 0.18)	13.00 (± 1.01)	15.27 (± 2.47)	14.27 (± 0.42)
Washed BM	43.57 (± 1.66)	0.91 (± 0.05)	1.04 (± 0.14)	16.23 (± 0.39)	18.50 (± 1.30)	19.75 (± 0.64)
SCCO ₂ BM	30.38 (± 0.62)	1.07 (± 0.12)	2.02 (± 0.35)	19.73 (± 0.30)	22.71 (± 0.54)	24.11 (± 0.85)

Fig. 6. SEM images of **a)** (100x) and **c)** (1000x) pristine BM, **b)** (100x) and **d)** (1000x) SCCO₂ treated BM, EDS F mapping of **e)** pristine, **f)** SCCO₂ treated BM, EDS spectrum of **g)** pristine BM and **h)** SCCO₂ treated BM.

Fig. 7. FTIR of PVDF films on Al foil after drying DMSO from the collector.

skeletal bending), 763 (CF₂ bending and skeletal bending), 795 (CH₂ rocking), 854 (CH out-of-plane deformation), 975 (CH out-of-plane deformation), 1149, 1209, 1383 and 1423 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of the α -PVDF [53]. Even though α -phase is well defined, Cai et al. [52] showed that vibrational bands at 840 and 510 cm⁻¹ are mutual for both β and γ phases. Bands at 1275 and 1234 cm⁻¹ are the characteristic vibrational bands that belong to β and γ phases, respectively. The presence of the β -phase was also confirmed by distinct peaks at 473, 1275, and 1431 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, the bands observed at 1234 cm⁻¹ and weak bands at 482, 833, 811, and 1429 cm⁻¹ are typically associated with the γ -phase, indicating that the recovered PVDF films exhibit a combination of α -, β -, and γ -phases. The phases of PVDF and their fractions are critically important for battery applications, particularly due to the electroactive β phase. The β phase primarily contributes to the dielectric, piezoelectric, ferroelectric, and pyroelectric properties of PVDF, making it the most electrically active phase. Conversely, the α phase is thermodynamically stable but less electrically active. Furthermore, the fraction of each PVDF phase is influenced significantly by solvent evaporation dynamics, with drying speed and solvent characteristics playing essential roles in determining the final phase composition [51,54–57].

XRD analyses were also used to determine phase changes of BM before and after the process and plotted in Fig. 8. BM contains LiNi_{0.3}Mn_{0.3}Co_{0.3}O₂ (NMC, pdf card no 00–062–0431), LiCoO₂ (LCO, pdf card no 01–083–9084), and graphite (pdf card no 00–056–0160) phases. Results showed that neither the washing process nor the SCCO₂ process affected the main phases present in BM. However, peak broadening was observed in the collected portion from the filter-1 after the SCCO₂ process.

Collected DMSO was also measured with ¹⁹F NMR to confirm PVDF presence. NMR spectra were matching with the literature [58–60] and confirmed the presence of PVDF. The characteristic signal centered at –91.1 ppm, plotted in Fig. 9, is assigned to the regular –CH₂CF₂–CH₂CF₂– (head-to-tail, H-T) sequences. The head-to-head (H-H, –CH₂CF₂–CF₂CH₂–) sequences, which are systematically followed by tail-to-tail (T-T, –CF₂CH₂–CH₂CF₂–) sequences, give rise to the resonances at –113 and –115.3 ppm.

Fig. 10 shows the ¹⁹F NMR spectrum of the water used for BM washing. Since the medium was water, NMR was not able to lock and do shimming, therefore, there is a slight shift from the actual peak position. However, chemical shifts at –72.8 and –74 ppm belong to the LiPF₆ [61]. It clearly shows that washing the pristine BM also removed the Li salt residuals in addition to the removal of CMC. This result also confirmed the conclusion from the elemental analysis. This might pave

Fig. 8. XRD patterns of pristine, washed, recovered (from the reactor), and recovered (from the filter) BM.

Fig. 9. ¹⁹F NMR spectrum (600 MHz, DMSO-H₆ solvent) of collected DMSO.

the way for a step-by-step recovery of battery materials before recycling valuable metals.

4. Conclusion

In this study, SCCO₂ with co-solvent DMSO was used to extract the PVDF binder from industrial BM at 70 °C, 80 bar with 15 min process time. The effect of co-solvent volume was investigated on the efficiency of recovery yield. The experimental results show that 55.6 % of the initial PVDF was able to recover when 4 ml of co-solvent was used. Moreover, when 4 ml of DMSO was used, 1.48 mL (± 0.52) of the co-solvent remained in the reactor, containing 8.1 mg of dissolved PVDF.

Fig. 10. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of washing water.

The SCCO_2 process enhanced the solubility of PVDF in DMSO while reducing the dissolution time drastically. It was also observed that PVDF remained dissolved in DMSO when temperature and pressure went back to the RT and 1 atm. Thus, 29.3 % and 26.3 % of the initial PVDF were able to separate with SCCO_2 and post-separation, respectively. It is worth mentioning that PVDF film recovered from post-separation needs further purification due to the presence of BM residual (10 %). The comparison experiment showed that PVDF from the BM was not able to dissolve in DMSO at RT in 18 days or 70 °C in 24 h at atmospheric conditions. On the other hand, PVDF successfully dissolved in DMSO with the help of SCCO_2 only in 15 min. Furthermore, SEM analysis indicated a substantial decrease in agglomeration upon the removal of the PVDF binder, leading to the dispersion of cathode particles into finer fragments.

Author statement

On behalf of all authors, I confirm that the manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yigit Akbaş: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martina Petranikova:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Burçak Ebin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: [Burçak Ebin reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Yigit Akbaş reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.].

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of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2025.134056>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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